

Table 2. Reaction of TM8089 to major diseases.

Disease	Reaction ^a			
	TM8089	TKM9	ADT36	IR50
Blast				
Field screening	R	S	R	HS
Artificial screening	MR	S	R	S
Brown spot	MR	MR	-	R
Bacterial blight	MR	MR	-	S
Neck blast	0	^b	MR	MR
Sheath rot	MR	MR	MR	MR
Glume discoloration	MR	MR	MR	MR

^a By the Standard evaluation system for rice. ^b Not tested.

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield data and yield component data from routine germplasm screening trials. Publication is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., multiple or unique resistances and tolerances, broad adaptability), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils

Effect of soil texture on rice growth and yield

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We compared growth and yield of PR106 in pots in three soils of different textures: clay loam, loam, and sandy loam. Physicochemical properties of soils (deter-

mined by procedures of Chopra and Kanwar) are given in Table 1.

Recommended nutrients were applied, standard management practices followed. Plant samples were collected at tillering and panicle initiation. Yield was measured at harvest and grain samples taken for chemical analysis. N was estimated by semi-micro Kjeldahl's method, P by the procedure of Koenig and Johnson, and K by flame photometer.

Root dry matter and grain yield were significantly higher in fine-textured clay loam than in loam or sandy loam soils (Table 2). Plants grown in sandy loam

soils showed poor root growth and gave lowest grain yield. The higher yield in clay loam soils can be attributed to their higher nutrient-supplying capacity (CEC 16.8). ■

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of cutting frequency on rice herbage yield

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We studied the effect of leaf cutting frequency on herbage yield, grain yield, and production components of deepwater rice under natural field conditions in 1988 wet season. Eight cutting frequencies and no cutting were arranged in a randomized complete block design with four replications (see table).

PG56 was sown at 120 kg seeds/ha onto plowed soil 20 May 1988. Seedling emergence was measured at end of May. The maximum water level was about 110 cm on 7 Nov 1988.

Herbage was collected by cutting at the collar level of the last fully developed leaves. The last cutting (130 d after emergence) was about 55 d before flowering.

Cutting at late growth stages and cutting more times significantly increased herbage yield. The highest dry herbage yield (2 t/ha) was with 3 cuttings at 40, 70, and 100 d after emergence.

Table 1. Physicochemical characteristics of the experimental soils.

	Clay loam	Loam	Sandy loam
pH (1:2)	8.1	8.3	8.5
EC (dS/m)	0.32	0.28	0.30
Organic carbon (%)	0.31	0.29	0.26
<i>Available nutrients (kg/ha)</i>			
N	160	140	130
P	7	6	6.5
K	265	240	210
Zn (ppm)	0.51	0.55	0.53
Sand (%)	25	51	57
Silt (%)	35	27	28
Clay (%)	39	21	14
CEC meq/100 g	16.8	12.2	8.3

Table 2. Effect of soil texture on grain yield, root dry matter, and nutrient uptake by rice.

Soil type	Root dry matter (g/pot)		Grain yield (g/pot)	Nutrients removed (g/pot)		
	At tillering	At panicle initiation		N	P	K
Sandy loam	4.2	6.8	14.7	10.7	0.05	0.15
Loam	4.5	7.2	17.9	12.1	0.05	0.16
Clay loam	5.2	7.9	23.1	15.3	0.07	0.21
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.3	1.6	1.3	0.01	0.02